

TRANSFERENCE AND COUNTERTRANSFERENCE IN THE PSYCHOANALYTIC CLINIC

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Natássia Helena Oliveira

Psychoanalyst. Psychotherapist. Email: natassiahelenaoliveira@gmail.com.

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Postdoctoral in Psychology. Philosopher. Psychopedagogue. Psychoanalyst. Email: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This work approaches the theme of transference and countertransference in psychoanalytic clinic, in an attempt to clarify how both occur and what mechanisms can be inferred for a better didactic exploration in favor of the therapeutic cure of the neurotic patient. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it explores the subject in its most intrinsic dynamics, involving being and non-being and even becoming relevant to therapeutic treatment processes. Its social relevance lies in clarifying to the general population how a psychoanalytic clinical treatment is designed and the dynamics that involve it. It is a bibliographical, factual, exploratory, descriptive research, based on classic authors who discuss the theme from the therapeutic action itself. What a patient transfers during therapy can be trivial, not least because the cathexis energy presented does not mean that everyone has to endure severe pain and complex conditions. As the Master of Vienna himself puts it, the transference is not always negative, meaning that feelings of hatred, rancor or unresolved violence are addressed to the doctor. It is concluded, from the material studied, that transference and countertransference are complex issues, because they involve a range of other aspects, of greater or lesser depth, and what stands out the most is the therapist's condition in knowing the transference dynamics and knowing how to apply the due didactic aspect to them, in view of the patient's interest in being cured of his neurotic disorder.

Keywords: Transfer; Countertransference; psychoanalytic clinic; resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoanalysis is a complex technique, demanding in terms of didactic knowledge and much more, that goes beyond the limits of common sense and enters a field that is not allowed [*and that cannot be confused with prohibited*], because it keeps portions of secrets that the

unconscious itself took care to hide and prevent access to the individual who believes to be its owner and this means that during the treatment a whole play of light and shadows permeate the listening process, producing, as a result, situations of conflict between the parties that are conventionally categorized as therapeutic transference and countertransference.

It should be noted that Psychoanalysis was born from the clinical practice of Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) and, as results and empirical manifestations emerged, the need for explanations for the phenomena observed during treatment sessions emerged. . It was from there that hypotheses of an explanatory nature began to appear, which later could be proven and transformed into theories capable of clarifying such and such abnormal behavior, and a doubt still affected Freud and his disciples, which was to know the etiology of the manifest behaviors. by those who suffered from nerves, the neurotics. What's more, was the anguish they complained of a *pathos* exclusive to them?

Much later, Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961) revealed that the illness from which neurotics suffered also affected normal individuals, with the difference that the former did not know how to deal with existential situations and, in this psychological imbalance they sought out the strangest solutions that were presented to their peers (Id., 2008).

One of these therapeutic situations that arise in the clinical field is *transference* , in which the patient transfers all of his tragic guilt to his therapist, demanding a balanced and extremely sensible posture on his part, until he identifies the dimension of what is being released on you and what kind of psychic image is reflecting to the neurotic. At this moment, the therapist becomes a mirror, through which the individual undergoing treatment projects an image that he believes to be of himself, since he has introjected all the values he disliked, coming from the one he thought he hated; but, that in silence he loved, because of the violence with which he scourged him, even in silence.

Against this situation, the therapist must know how to return to the patient all the load of hate, disguised as love, that he throws at himself, a process that is categorized as *transference*; and, if you don't, what you have as a result is a patient faking a cure, simply to get rid of an inefficient and ineffective treatment, from a clinical-therapeutic point of view.

TRANSFER AND COUNTER TRANSFER

Transference, according to what Freud explained, after its discovery is an essential part of the analytic treatment, but it proves to be difficult to interpret because its occurrence during

the treatment is not predictable, and can even be masked by the patient, which presumes a his right, given that the motivation for therapeutic follow-up is not the imposition of a cure method on the neurotic, but a mechanism in which one seeks to strengthen the individual ego until he himself can provide a solution to his conflicting confrontations of an intimate nature.

In this regard, it has already been stated that the occurrence of transference is due to the existence of a weakened ego and, based on this, it is up to the analyst to discover the dimension of this unconscious action that is directed towards his person. This is how Freud (2006) argues about the aforementioned action in which,

We must make up our minds to distinguish a 'positive' from a 'negative' transference, the transference of affectionate feelings from hostile ones, and to treat the two types of transference to the physician separately. Positive transference is still divisible into transference of friendly or affectionate feelings, which are admissible to consciousness, and transference of extensions of these feelings into the unconscious (FREUD [1912] 2006, p. 171).

Freud is dealing with an explanation without having knowledge about how transferences happen, and what he reveals is their existence and the dimension that is presented to the therapist, without him being able to dynamize the work of counter transference in a didactic way, previously studied. It reveals that the transference process can be disguised in several aspects and it is in these conjectures that the challenges are present, because the doctor himself can interpret in a different way the material that comes to him through the patient and provoke a resistance in fact, not knowing how to direct it back.

What a patient transfers during therapy can be something trivial, even because the cathexial energy presented does not mean that everyone has to endure severe pain and complex conditions. As Freud himself points out, transference is not always negative, with this understanding that feelings of hatred, resentment or unresolved violence are directed towards the physician. Andrade reiterates that,

We transfer interests, emotions, fantasies, anxiety, guilt, from one object to another; they are all trends linked to the process of symbol formation. Therefore, in our work [*of therapeutic analysis*], the conflict reappears, is transferred to the therapist, and when it reappears, it can be worked on. [...] In the beginning, the transference was looked at to see how it appeared, and Freud showed this to the patient – he showed how it was in the past and how it was repeating itself there (ANDRADE, 2012, p. 2).

What Freud did was lead the patient to confront reality and how his unconscious was distorting the original scene, in an attempt to find a resolution to a conflict that now appeared

symbolized and not necessarily real. This situation is quite complex and of intense difficulty to explain and interpret, as well as to synthesize, because Physis *has* a human developmental pattern that is linear and certain experiences that happen, inevitably, to the human being needs that its intellectual scope be prepared to receive the dose of unexpected violence that can overtake you.

When transference occurs, of any nature [*positive and/or negative*], this is a form of communication from the unconscious demanding an understanding of what happened and, not effectively, desiring a *cure*, in the literal sense of the term; starting with the fact that nothing will [*nor can*] erase the episode that left an indelible mark of tragic guilt on the individual's spirit. Being more didactic, transference should be understood as a way of atoning for guilt and the *positive and negative expressions* are clinical interpretations.

Based on such individual interpretations, the therapist begins to work on a terrain that is difficult to access and quite delicate, which is countertransference, which, in Andrade's conception,

Countertransference [*is*] something that happens to the analyst and that can intervene in his work. The analyst's reactions to his patient were always seen as something very serious that strongly intervened in observation, in capturing the patient. It was something that happened to get in the way, and that's why a lot of care was needed. Many authors went so far as to say, emphatically, that the remedy for countertransference was for the analyst to go back to the couch. In other words: the feelings, the analyst's reactions to the patient, even the fantasies that occur to him in the session were seen as obstacles to his understanding of what was happening to the patient; they were always seen as the analyst's difficulties that he needed to detect so as not to harm the analysis (ANDRADE, 2012, p. 4).

It is necessary to clarify that the transference does not disturb or prevent the development of the analytical-therapeutic treatment, starting with the fact that, we are dealing with a human being, dictated by reason and emotion, a dichotomy for which there are no defined parameters for its occurrence, much less at what time; bearing in mind that each one's previous life story is a *Pandora's Box* , with no way of predicting what evils might come out of it and what is the dimension of its potential for destruction.

Add to this, as a preponderant factor of the therapy, the fact that when the transference happens it is because the patient is convinced that he can trust his doctor and more, his ego is strengthened enough to expose feelings, thoughts and desires that cause shame. This is where the professional must be attentive, because the countertransference can be understood by the patient from the [*apparently*] most innocent gesture that can be expressed; it does not

necessarily have to be a verbalized judgment. The neurotic is so, for possessing and, sometimes, presenting a very fragile egoic structure, living divided between guilt and shame and also the fear of the judgment of others.

It is not countertransference that demands a high level of intellectual preparation from the analyst; it is transference, as it is from there that the entire initial healing process begins to trigger and allow the first steps in this direction to be achieved. Freud understood this perfectly and when he evolved with therapeutic practice, starting from the clinic, in which he created the method of treatment where the therapist positions himself with his back to the patient, it was precisely to prevent the latter from understanding his facial expressions as judgments. of value and, in the clinic, as a countertransference, preventing the progress of the analytic cure. This is a problem that leads the patient to make a value judgment about the medical attitude based on his egodystonic.

In a way, Freud understood that the transference, before being synthesized by the analyst as such, must be seen as a revelation by the patient, a confession of something terrible [so terrible] that he kept hidden, in secret, until that *moment*. However, the fact that he reveals it does not mean that it bothers him more or less or that it does not awaken ambiguous, shameful or painful feelings; only that he feels that he has found someone to whom he can express his *pathos* without running the risk of being judged.

The countertransference would be in the action of applying an entire intellectual scope of knowledge of the causes that led the patient to be so ashamed of what happened and, still, guilty of what he went through. The patient's free associations, guided by the therapist, are what will allow the approximation of a successful overcoming of the trauma, allowing one to reach the level of psychoanalytic cure, a complex situation, because the time this takes is unknown, showing that a psychoanalyst is not a priest nor that the analytical treatment is a religious confession. The clinical analyst is not given the power, *in constesti*, of absolution, of individual guilt.

Freud (1912) will state that,

The solution to the riddle is that transference to the doctor is appropriate for resistance to treatment only in so far as it is a question of negative or positive transference of repressed erotic impulses. If we 'remove' the transference by making it conscious, we are only disconnecting those two components of the emotional act from the doctor's person; the other component, admissible to conscience and irreproachable, persists, constituting the vehicle of success in psychoanalysis, exactly as it is in other methods of treatment (FREUD [1912] 2006, p. 172).

What Freud clarifies, for didactic purposes, is that transference could not be seen by analysts as a stumbling block or even an obstacle to treatment. All this, at the time, sounded very disturbing, because Psychoanalysis, as a treatment method, was being built from a clinical-therapeutic praxis, that is, first the technicians were faced with the occurrence of the phenomenon and had to seek explanations for them. and, in the absence of such, they had to create didactic and pedagogical mechanisms that could clarify what happened in the offices with the patients during the therapeutic sessions. This represented an infinite challenge, in which the articles of the time only sought to guide physicians who practiced psychoanalysis as a psychological treatment to be patient and try to observe such manifestations more deeply.

In his early days, Freud dreamed of the possibility of a cure; but, over time, it was understood that Psychoanalysis had become a science and, as such, it needed to know, in greater depth, its target object of study, the human being and his psychological nuances. In this investigative process, he finds numerous details that were in other fields of knowledge; but that, ironically, it was only from the inferences of Psychoanalysis that they could better express the intrinsic world of this being and, likewise, understand the environment in which the being was immersed and how this influenced him to be and act in a way and another, or still, hiding its metaphysical essence.

TRANSFERENCE AND COUNTERTRANSFERENCE THERAPY IN THE PSYCHOANALYTIC CLINIC

Transference and countertransference are aspects of psychotherapeutic clinical treatment and, when they occur, the most that the analyst has to do is to have the dexterity to continue the treatment within the precept of greater technical viability, aiming at therapeutic cure, which can be understood as a strengthening of the individual ego and, in the wake of this, conflicts tend to be resolved, no longer causing spiritual discomfort, affecting the entire affective and social life.

Stekel, who tries to clarify this issue, raises the clarifying question that,

The question whether transference is provoked by psychoanalysis must be answered in the negative. A pertinent comment by Freud [*in this regard*] is: psychoanalysis does not create transference, it only reveals it. We must assume that similar phenomena of affective transfer and bonding with other people are part of everyday phenomena, which then makes life comprehensible to us (STEKEL, [1911] 2017, sp).

Stekel's exposition demonstrates that transference is a component of human life and that, in the treatment given by psychoanalysis, it takes on a complex aspect, because it involves a whole didactics that is based on the analyst's technical knowledge and on his individual preparation, in which his The ego needs to be balanced to the point of avoiding the pitfalls set by the very condition of interpreting the symbolic elements that are revealed in the transference expression.

The neurotic always presents himself with a very intense libidinal load, with which he cannot deal objectively [*or subjectively*], leading all this unresolved feeling and this unresolved energy to cause the symptoms of malaise that are revealed in the clinic. during the analytical treatment. In this aspect, transference happens spontaneously and unconsciously, given that he cannot find balance in his own state of being.

All this reveals that, in its beginnings, transference was understood and interpreted as a form of negative resistance on the part of the patient, in which his interest was to prevent the consummation of the treatment. And, on the part of the enemies of Psychoanalysis [*which were not few*] was the interpretation that this was a creation of the analysts, in order to justify the extension, *ad infinitum* , of the therapeutic consultation.

These are details of understanding that prove to be challenging for Psychoanalysis, because it is not born in the laboratory, as a theory; was already born in the field of medical practice and the phenomena were being observed and analyzed in such a way that an understanding could be reached and in order to produce knowledge about them, numerous previous works had to be analyzed in which any manifestation that approached could be described. what happened at the clinic with the nervous patients.

Classical literature, especially [*Greek and Shakespearean*] tragedies, were the most fertile fields where an archaeological search could be carried out in this sense, not without also passing by literary authors such as León Tostói (1828-1910) and Fyodor Dostoyevsky (1821.-1881), Balzac (1799-1850) and philosophers such as Plato (428/427-348/347 BC), Schopenhauer (1788-1860) and Nietzsche (1854-1900).

However, it remained to know, at first hand, if this occurrence was something inherent to human beings and then, the reasons that provoked it and, in the next step, to transform all this into therapeutic clinical material. The task was epic, and no wonder it posed such an intellectual challenge to psychoanalysts in Freud's day.

Freud, in his article written on transference and countertransference, in 1912, states that,

In the process of looking for the libido that had escaped the patient's consciousness, we entered the realm of the unconscious. The reactions we provoke reveal, at the same time, some of the characteristics that we have come to know from the study of dreams. Unconscious impulses do not wish to be remembered in the way the treatment wants them to be, but strive to reproduce themselves in accordance with the timelessness of the unconscious and its capacity for hallucination. As with dreams, the patient regards the awakening products of his unconscious impulses as contemporary and real; seeks to put his passions into action without regard to the real situation. The doctor tries to compel him to adjust these emotional impulses to the nexus of the treatment and his life history, to subject them to intellectual consideration and to understand them in the light of their psychic value. This struggle between doctor and patient, between intellect and instinctual life, between understanding and seeking action, is fought almost exclusively in the phenomena of transference (FREUD [1912] 2006, pp. 173-4).

Freud will clarify that transference is the most relevant element of psychoanalytic therapy and its recognition of value is what will determine the course of success, leading to a cure, to a proximity to the unveiling of the etiological causes of hysteria. In this, from the appearance of this, the analysis must unfold on the interpretation of what the patient is resorting to in favor of resistance.

The possibility of a possible reach over everything that goes on in the analytic clinic lies in maintaining a tension between what is shareable – the words that are common and those that are singular, specific to each one – and something that cannot be shared unless be through art, or through transference. Hence arises the need to develop therapeutic actions that allow the patient to symbolize his *pathos* through other symbolic elements about which the analyst has knowledge to interpret them through the free association of ideas, without any kind of prior mastery. Possibly, nothing that is revealed through this auxiliary technique, applied to the treatment, is reducible to any scientific narrative (PALHARES, 2008).

As soon as,

You have to live, experience; what is imposed are the forces of the event, the unfolding of life. In this unfolding, transference occurs spontaneously in all human relationships, since this movement from the inside to the outside, from the outside to the inside, is incessant. Soon, transference emerges from life, because it will point to an endless coming-to-be; in that sense it is structuring. In the psychoanalytic clinic, it starts to be welcomed as the living translation of human bonds, and it is from there that the maintenance and validity of the treatment take root (PALHARES, 2008, p. 103).

Even after more than a century of studies and discoveries about transference and countertransference, both continue to challenge the psychoanalytic clinic due to the fact that times have changed and so have social pressures. If, in Freud's time, people living under an

austere Victorian regime of chastity and censorship were interpreted as the etiological agent of hysteria, today, all the freedom conquered has not been able to solve the anguish crises that human beings experience. and that, in their most obscure fields, they are marked by the same problems as always, the struggle between libido and moral censorship.

The need for the analyst's therapeutic training, well directed towards self-understanding, is still the cornerstone of his practice, because,

Unconscious fantasies will appear in the relationship with the analyst, but always with new meanings, as this is a new relationship, never repeated. It is always an experience, there in the session, that finds its meaning there in the relationship of the moment. The meanings are discovered and presented to the patient. It has no key, no established code (ANDRADE, 2012, p. 3).

Andrade sets a special condition for the therapist technician, in which surprise is the key element of the therapy, since there is no way to perform any anticipation about the future, while the treatment lasts. The human unconscious works towards making the individual happy and at ease with his existence; for this, it is necessary to eliminate the material that has not been properly processed for reasons beyond the person's own being and that causes spiritual discomfort, preventing a good existential relationship with oneself and with peers.

What are transfers? They are new editions or facsimiles of impulses and fantasies which are awakened and made conscious during progress in the analysis; but they have this peculiarity, which is a particular characteristic, that they substitute the person of the doctor for some primitive person. To put it in other words: a whole series of psychological experiences are relived, not as belonging to the past, but applied to the doctor in the present moment. [...] Dora acted out an essential fragment of her memories instead of remembering them (Freud, 1905[1901]/2006, p. 133).

By considering transferences as manifest mechanisms of resistance, this is the first step towards taking due care in the treatment sequence, because as SS Pope Pius XII states (1953), the unconscious will prove resistant to the therapist's interference, believing that the patient still does not have his ego properly strengthened to expose the cause of his pain, which may be the event that led to the traumatic factor.

Once the transference takes place, from then on, it is up to the analyst to be very careful in his interpretation and also pay attention to verifying whether the patient is able to receive the cathexial load arising from the doctor's response, clarification on the motives that lie underground in the exposed personality. Once the neuralgic point that causes psychogenic pain is exposed, this does not mean that the treatment will flow more progressively; it simply refers

to the fact that the paths to be followed by the therapist are more complex, with the need to know which directions were taken by the unconscious itself so that a *supposed emotional balance* could be achieved and maintained.

Stekel, in his 1911 article, clarifies that the analyst has the responsibility of mastering the concepts related to transference and establishing empirical knowledge about the different modes of its manifestation, in order to be able to carry out a satisfactory therapeutic dynamic. For him,

Knowing the different forms of transference is, for the psychoanalyst, the basic condition for successful work. Without accurate knowledge of the transfer, the analysis is stuck in a dead end and does not move forward. Without knowledge of the transference, its solution and its return to primary object love, the continuity of the treatment becomes impossible (STEKEL, [1911] 2017, sp).

The aforementioned author expresses the need for *precise knowledge*, and the rest of his speech can be interpreted as being relevant for the therapist to focus on the investigation of the primary causes that led to the occurrence of the transference, understanding this as a form of resistance arising from the unconscious, a form of ego protection.

In this sense, Nietzsche alerts to the fact that,

Behind his cave lurks another cavern even deeper—a vaster, stranger world, richer than the surface, a depth behind every bottom, beneath every 'foundation'. All philosophy is a philosophy of the surface, this is the conviction of the solitary: 'there is something arbitrary in this if you stop here, looking back and around you, if you do not dig deeper here and throw away the tools — and all this breeds distrust'. Every philosophy hides another philosophy; every opinion is a hiding place, every word a new mask" (NIETZSCHE, 2006, p. 220).

What is a patient trying to hide when he manifests his symbolic resistance through transference? And more, what do you expect as a cure from your doctor? These are questions raised by Nietzsche when he wrote his aphorism, in 1889, which, it can be said, had nothing to do with Psychoanalysis; however, in it, the German philosopher refers to psychologists and writing as a way of disguising what he actually feels.

Countertransference is a situation in which the emotions that the therapist experiences in the course of an analysis, in relation to the patient, are and are related to circumstances felt in his own life, which affected him consciously and unconsciously. This reveals that his understanding of himself and his emotional state are too incomplete, to the point that he confuses the relationship between doctor and patient, interpreting it as an informal relationship.

Freud argues that,

This phenomenon, which occurs constantly and which is, as we know, one of the foundations of psychoanalytic theory, can be evaluated from two points of view, that of the doctor and that of the patient who needs it. For the physician, the phenomenon provides valuable enlightenment and a useful warning against any tendency to countertransference that may be present in his own mind. He must recognize that the patient's falling in love is induced by the analytic situation and must not be attributed to the charms of his own person; so that he has no reason to be proud of such an 'achievement', as it would be called outside analysis. And it is always good to remember this (Freud, 1915, p. 209-210).

For Freud, countertransference must be understood as a source of information about the patient, having its causes and effects on the patient, not involving any responsibility and participation of the analyst (COELHO, 2002). He means with the terms *responsibility and participation*, that the analyst must let the phenomenon mentioned above happen in the most natural way possible, as part of the ongoing treatment, which demands maturity from the analyst and a work of analysis, self-analysis and Analytical supervision very well directed.

According to Coelho (2002, p. 141)

Sanctor Ferenzi defines countertransference as everything that is consciously, preconsciously or unconsciously thought, felt, desired or fantasized by the analyst. Therefore, it does not define it only as blind spots or unknown aspects of the analyst that were not worked on in his personal analysis. All this can be captured by the patient, as long as we believe that both the analyst captures the patient's unconscious and the latter is able to do the same with his analyst.

This is a dangerous question posed by Ferenzi, in which he turns both of them into accomplices in a delicate process, in which, on the one hand, the patient's, there is a condition of trust established towards the person of his therapist and casts on him your pain as a way to find a cure. In the countertransference process, it is expected that the analyst has enough strength to work with the contents that he receives from the analysand and analyze them, creating a treatment expansion mechanism in such a way that it creates a structural bond from the knowledge of the symptoms expressed and transferred to you and convert this whole mechanism into a psychoanalytic healing potential.

According to Coelho (2002), Bion considered the emergence of countertransference as a manifestation of the analyst's unconscious and, therefore, it could be harmful and could only be consciously perceived and reflected by the analyst outside the session. This is a different situation, because during the moment of dialogue and interpretation of the contents, both are immersed in a very unique condition of simultaneous and reciprocal action, and even Freud's

analyzes regarding transference and countertransference reveal this care to be taken when outside the analytical session, in which the ability to understand the phenomenon shows the analyst's technical maturity or his immaturity and even the deficiency in his therapeutic training process.

Countertransference is defined as a relational phenomenon of the analytical clinic, as it arises *as a result of the patient's influence* and, therefore, is closely linked to transference, a central aspect of the analytical method (ZAMBELLI et al, 2013), in which there is a need for externalization. of what is creating barriers to the full development of the emotional state of being.

Even if, in the psychoanalytic clinic, transference has the intention of healing, of helping to overcome the deepest traumas and that, in a strange and not so understood way, it returns to conscious reality, demanding clarification about what remains hidden, the therapist needs to work with the hypothesis that something much more painful is being kept out of sight and, it's not about understanding what it is; but *why* .

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Throughout this article, we sought to address the subject of transference and countertransference in the psychoanalytic clinic, and what can be seen is that this is a subject that is very dear to Psychoanalysis and psychoanalysts since Freud detected its occurrence, already in the early days of his clinical practice. . It is a complex subject, because it involves a range of other aspects, of greater or lesser depth, and what stands out most is the therapist's condition in knowing the transference dynamics and knowing how to apply the due didactic aspect to them, in view of the interest of the patient in being cured of his neurotic disorder.

Freud and Stekel are adamant about the need to know about transference processes and how to act based on their clinical manifestation. However, theoretical clarification is too little to demand a correct posture from the analyst, and it is up to this that his training be guided under conditions of supervision that enable him to know himself and his personality disorders.

The sentence that F. Nietzsche launches and that Lou-Salomé (1861-1937) takes as a value for himself is a burden, *ad absurdum* , for the patient and the therapist, in which, what truths both want to keep hidden under the veil of resistance ? For the analyst, it is up to the care to explore, from then on, through free association, the dynamics of the thought that was

expressed, letting the patient lead the treatment, revealing the depth of his spirit and his unconscious he is free to go.

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